

Study of Hypothyroidism in Pregnancy

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Abstract:

Thyroid hormones of the fetus exclusively comes from mothers in early pregnancy, indicating that maternal hypothyroidism has a close-knit relationship with fetal growth and neuropsychological development. Hypothyroidism is one of the most common endocrinopathies during pregnancy. Thyroid dysfunction is a common disorder in pregnancy which affects both maternal and fetal outcomes. There are very less and limited data on prevalence of hypothyroidism during pregnancy from India because no such big study done till now. A total 60 cases were included in the study. The age ranged from 18 to 45 years . Serum TSH value was tested in 1st trimester between 6-10 weeks period of gestation for all pregnant women. The estimation of free T4 levels was done to reclassify those with thyroid dysfunction as subclinical or overt hypothyroidism. Subclinical Hypothyroidism were 16.66 %, Overt Hypothyroidism were 11.66 % Pregnant women.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, Pregnancy.

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Introduction

Function of the thyroid gland is affected by pregnancy is associated with maternal/fetal health [1]. In the first trimester of pregnancy, human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) stimulates a transient elevation in maternal serum concentration of free thyroxine (fT4), which is reflected by a decrease in levels of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH); during this trimester, maternal serum TSH concentrations are significantly lower than pre-conception levels. Following, serum levels of fT4 decrease by 10%, and maternal level of TSH gradually increases to normal values. In addition, mid-gestation rise in serum concentrations of thyroxine binding globulin (TBG) leads to significant increase in both total thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy [2-4]. In this context daily iodide consumption increased along with a reduction in TSH levels [5] and immunosuppression inherent throughout pregnancy, leads to decrease in level of maternal thyroid autoantibodies levels [6]. The pregnancy-related changes in thyroid physiology make diagnosis of thyroid disorder difficult, because it can simulate signs and symptoms of physiological changes of pregnancy.7 Symptoms of heat intolerance, sluggishness, fatigue, and examination findings of tachycardia, edema, hair changes, and weight gain are common to pregnancy and thyroid disease much in same way. [7] The management of therefore based principally on biochemical measures. Thyroid dysfunction during pregnancy is

associated with adverse maternal complications like miscarriages, anaemia complicating pregnancy, pre-eclampsia, abruptio-placentae, postpartum haemorrhage and foetal complications like premature birth, low birth weight ,increased neonatal respiratory distress .Maternal and foetal hypothyroidism can also result in irreversible brain damage with mental retardation and neurologic abnormalities which justifies screening for thyroid dysfunction during early pregnancy with interventional levothyroxine therapy for thyroid hypofunction. Pregnancy results in a number of important physiological and hormonal changes that alter thyroid function mainly due to the influence of two main hormone; human chronic gonadotropin (HCG) and estrogen. Thyroid dysfunction is often overlooked in pregnancy because of the non-specific symptoms and the hyper metabolic state of pregnancy. Therefore, this study was conducted with sincere effort to throw some light on this topic.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted in OBGY department of tertiary care medical college and hospital. A total 60 cases were included in the study. The age ranged from 18 to 45 years . Serum TSH value was tested in 1st trimester between 6-10 weeks period of gestation for all pregnant women. The estimation of free T4 levels was done to reclassify those with

thyroid dysfunction as subclinical or overt hypothyroidism.

Inclusion Criteria

- Primi and multigravida belonging to any age group
- Singleton pregnancy
- Patients in the first trimester

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-gestational hypothyroidism.

- Multiple pregnancy
- Gestational trophoblastic disease.
- Hyperthyroid Women

All subjects enrolled in the study as per the inclusion criteria will be subjected to a detailed history and clinical examination using a predesigned proforma.

Results

66.66 % of Pregnant women were in age group of 26-35years.

Table 1: Age groups of Pregnant women

Age groups(years)	Frequency n=60	Percentage
<25	05	8.33 %
26-35	40	66.66 %
36-45	15	25 %

Table 2: Thyroid dysfunction in pregnant women

Thyroid dysfunction	TSH (mIU/L)	F T4(mcg/dl)
Euthyroid	0.4-3.5	Normal
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	>3.5	Normal
Overt Hypothyroidism	>3.5	Decreased

Table 3: Types of Hypothyroidism

Thyroid dysfunction	Frequency n=60	Percentage
Euthyroid	43	71.66 %
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	10	16.66 %
Overt Hypothyroidism	07	11.66 %

Table 3 shows 71.66 % pregnant women were Euthyroid. 16.66 % were having Subclinical Hypothyroidism and 11.66 % had Overt Hypothyroidism.

Discussion

Thyroid dysfunction during pregnancy has an immense impact on maternal and fetal outcomes. [8,9] More importantly, children born to hypothyroid mothers have a poor intellectual function during the latter part of their life. Low IQS in infants of even very mild hypothyroid women have been reported. There is an increased risk of preeclampsia placental abruption, intra-uterine growth restriction, prematurity and intra-uterine fetal demise. Therefore, the majority of the developed countries have national neonatal screening program.[10] The prevalence of hypothyroidism is more in Asian countries compare with the west, it varies from 2.5% from the West to 11% from India.[11,12] Rao et al. found hypothyroidism in 4.2% of recurrent pregnancy less which is statistically significant.14 Sahu et al. have done thyroid function in the second trimester and reported prevalence of thyroid disorder especially OH and SCH 6.47%.[13,14] Dhanwal et al. from Delhi in 2013 reported hypothyroidism prevalence of 14.3% with cut-off value of 4.5 mIU/L as the upper limit of normal in a cohort of 100 pregnant women. In another study from Delhi Nagia AS et al. in 2013

reported a prevalence rate of 12% amongst 400 pregnant women. Thyroid disorder is a common in pregnancy and affects both maternal and fetal outcomes. There are limited data on prevalence of hypothyroidism during pregnancy from India.[15] The overall prevalence of hypothyroidism varies from 0.3-11.1% with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) being commoner than overt hypothyroidism.[16] due to their nonspecific symptoms and hypermetabolic state of pregnancy thyroid disorders are often overlooked in pregnancy most of the time. Maternal hypothyroidism has been associated with adverse pregnancy complications as well as detrimental effects upon fetal neurocognitive development. Specific maternal adverse outcome includes anemia, abortion, preterm labour, gestational hypertension, preeclampsia and placental abruption. Fetal complications include prematurity, intrauterine foetal growth restriction, intrapartum foetal distress, foetal demise.

Conclusion

In our study Euthyroid were 71.66 %, Subclinical Hypothyroidism were 16.66%, Overt Hypothyroidism were 11.66% subjects. Early detection, prompt initiation of treatment and adequate follow-up of hypothyroidism in pregnancy is very important for the fetal and maternal well being.

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